

AGILE GOVERNANCE IN THE POPULATION ADMINISTRATION SERVICE SYSTEM IN DISDUKCAPIL BANDUNG REGENCY

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Abstract

Population administration is a crucial aspect in public services that requires a system that is fast, accurate, and responsive to the dynamics of change. The concept of Agile Governance is an innovative approach to improving the quality of population administration services, particularly in the Population and Civil Registration Service (Disdukcapil) of Bandung Regency. This study aims to analyze the implementation of Agile Governance, identify supporting and inhibiting factors, and evaluate its contribution to the effectiveness of public services. The method used is descriptive qualitative with data collection techniques through in-depth interviews, observations, and documentation studies. The success of the implementation is analyzed through three main indicators of Key Performance Indicators (KPI), namely velocity lead time (data processing speed), cycle time & response time (system efficiency), and user satisfaction. The results of the study show that Disdukcapil Bandung has adopted various innovations, including digital service innovations (SAKEDAP and Anjungan Dukcapil Mandiri), information transparency, and flexibility in decision-making. However, challenges in the form of limited human resources, low digital literacy of the community, and limited access to services in remote areas are still major obstacles. This study concludes that Agile Governance contributes significantly to improving the efficiency, accountability, and responsiveness of population services. Recommendations include the integration of real-time data-based digital systems, strengthening employee capacity in Agile Leadership, and increasing community involvement in service evaluation in order to realize more adaptive

and inclusive public services.

Keywords: Agile Governance, Population Administration, Key Performance Indicators, Public Services, Service Digitalization, Disdukcapil Bandung Regency.

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving digital era, public sector organizations are required to adopt an adaptive, responsive, and collaborative governance system. One approach that is relevant to this challenge is Agile Governance, namely agile, iterative, and participatory governance, which was initially developed in software development practices but is now starting to be applied to the realm of public organization governance (Luna & Morais, 2009).

The application of Agile principles in government is intended to increase bureaucratic efficiency, accelerate response to community needs, and strengthen service accountability. In a study conducted by the OECD (2020), it is explained that adapting the agile model can encourage innovation and better integration of public services amidst the complexity of the needs of modern society. This is relevant to the conditions in Indonesia, where public bureaucracy is still often considered slow, hierarchical, and less responsive to rapidly changing social dynamics (Wijayanti, 2021).

One of the most strategic service areas in regional government is population administration services. The Population and Civil Registration Service (Disdukcapil) of Bandung Regency is an institution that has an important role in providing accurate and integrated population data. The high volume of services, demands for speed of service, and the need for cross-sector data integration encourage the importance of implementing more agile and adaptive governance.

However, until now, there has been very limited empirical research that specifically examines the application of Agile Governance principles in the context of population services at the local level. This is the research gap and the novelty of this scientific article. Departing from the literature review, this article aims to

analyze how Agile Governance principles are applied in the population data service system at the Disdukcapil of Bandung Regency, and to identify supporting and inhibiting factors.

Based on the problems that have been described, the formulation of the problem proposed is:

How is the application of Agile Governance principles in the population data service system at the Disdukcapil of Bandung Regency? And what are the factors that support and inhibit the implementation of these principles?

The initial hypothesis of this study is that the partial implementation of Agile Governance can improve the effectiveness of population services, but the implementation is still hampered by a hierarchical bureaucratic structure and limited understanding of agile principles at the implementing level. Thus, this article is expected to provide scientific contributions to the development of adaptive and responsive governance studies, as well as become a practical reference in improving the quality of public services based on population data at the regional level.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a descriptive qualitative design with a case study approach in the Population and Civil Registration Service (Disdukcapil) of Bandung Regency. This approach was chosen because the researcher wanted to explore in depth the reality of the application of Agile Governance principles in the public service system, especially population data services, and understand the various social, technical, and organizational dynamics that influence it.

Data collection was carried out through three main techniques, namely:

- (1) in-depth interviews with Disdukcapil employees at various levels (structural officials and implementing staff),
- (2) non-participatory observation of the service process at the counter and online applications, and

(3) documentation studies of performance reports, internal policies, and service data. Informants were selected purposively with consideration of direct involvement in the service process and policy making.

The research instruments used were semi-structured interview guidelines, open observation sheets, and document checklists. The researcher also acted as the main instrument that actively collected data from the field and interpreted the observed phenomena.

The data analysis technique follows the interactive model of Miles and Huberman, which includes three main stages:

- (1) data reduction, which is the process of filtering and summarizing important data from the field,
- (2) presenting data in the form of thematic narratives based on analysis indicators, and
- (3) drawing conclusions and verification, to find meaning, patterns, and links between findings. To measure the effectiveness of the implementation of Agile Governance, this study uses the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) framework, which includes three main problem assessments, namely:
 - (1) Velocity (speed of service process),
 - (2) Lead time (length of service waiting time from the beginning of the application to being received), and
 - (3) Satisfaction (level of public satisfaction with the service).

These indicators are analyzed qualitatively to determine whether the agile principles are truly implemented substantively at the Bandung Regency Population and Civil Registry Office.

The study was conducted from March to April 2024 at the Disdukcapil head office and several administrative area service points to represent the geographical variations of the Bandung Regency area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aims to analyze the effectiveness of the implementation of Agile Governance principles in population data services at the Bandung Regency

Population and Civil Registry Office. The results of the data analysis show that although the agency has formally attempted to implement an agile approach, there are various obstacles that interfere with its effectiveness. The analysis was conducted using three main indicators in the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) framework, namely velocity, lead time, and satisfaction.

1. Velocity (Speed of Service Process)

Velocity is measured by the time required to process administrative requests, from population registration to data validation. Observation results show that basic services such as e-KTP recording can now be completed in 10-15 minutes, much faster than in previous years which took more than an hour. However, more complex services such as the issuance of birth certificates or marriage certificates still face delays due to limited human resources and uneven system access in 270 villages/sub-districts.

Interviews with officers showed that service acceleration is highly dependent on individual competence and network conditions. In remote areas, service velocity is much lower due to transportation constraints and a lack of trained officers. This shows that agile principles have not been applied evenly across all work areas.

2. Lead Time (Service Process Waiting Time)

Lead time refers to the time between a request for a service by the public and the service being received. Urban communities report an average lead time of 1-2 days for basic services. However, in rural areas with difficult geographic conditions, waiting times can reach 3-5 days, or even more. This is influenced by the unbalanced distribution of operational personnel and dependence on online systems that are not yet fully understood by residents.

In interviews and FGDs conducted, many residents expressed difficulty in understanding online procedures, as well as uncertainty regarding the mobile service schedule. This indicates that the principle of "responsiveness" in Agile Governance has not been optimally implemented.

3. Satisfaction (Public Satisfaction Level)

An internal survey conducted by the Population and Civil Registry Office showed

that around 90% of respondents were satisfied with the services in general, especially regarding e-KTP services and online applications. However, there was still an imbalance in perception between urban and rural residents. Villagers complained about the lack of assistance in using technology and limited service facilities.

From an agile perspective, community satisfaction is a key indicator of success because it indicates the match between service output and beneficiary expectations. Therefore, although satisfaction figures appear high, there is great room for improvement in service quality in areas with access gaps.

KPI Network Diagram Analysis

The visualization of interview and observation results is presented in the form of a thematic network diagram that illustrates the relationship between service barriers and KPI indicators. This diagram shows that barriers such as low officer competence, community digital gaps, and difficult geographic access are interrelated and directly affect velocity, lead time, and satisfaction.

The following are the results of the KPI thematic network analysis that illustrate the strengthening of the interview results of informants, both individual snowballs and service user groups:

Figure 1. Thematic Network Diagram of KPI Implementation in Agile Governance, related to

Velocity;

Still constrained by the time of administrative services for KTP, KK, especially Marriage Certificates and Birth Certificates, there are still weaknesses in specific responses in 270 villages, not yet reflecting the implementation of agile principles and effective administrative service principles for the Bandung Regency area as a whole.

Figure 2. Thematic Network Diagram of KPI Implementation in Agile Governance,

related to

Lead Time:

A very strong causal and thematic relationship illustrates that the speed of service still encounters obstacles, because the three important factors still need improvement and system consistency, the quality of human resources still needs training, and services that are very lacking in geography-based services, transportation, and community quality that still need assistance.

The following are the results of the analysis depicted by the thematic network diagram related to the breadth of service achievements of the Civil Registry Service linked to the results of interviews and observations of the opinions of consumers or the community using the service, as follows:

Figure 3. Thematic Network Diagram of KPI Implementation in Agile Governance, related to

Satisfaction:

Source: Research results, 2024

Customer Satisfaction reflects the success of an agile system that is oriented towards rapid iteration, responsive to citizen needs, and increased empathy. As a sign of a shift from bureaucracy to value-based public services. The obstacles faced by Disdukcapil services, towards the community whose quality of technological knowledge still greatly requires humanistic assistance, and proactive and standby

Service Posts in villages that are difficult to reach by Technology.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study are in line with the findings of Luna & Morais (2009), which stated that the success of Agile Governance is greatly influenced by the readiness of organizational culture, collaboration between sectors, and active participation of service users. In addition, the KPI theory proposed by Parmenter (2015) validates that the success of agile transformation is not only measured by the speed of the process, but also by the value of the services provided and the public satisfaction created.

The overall picture provided by the diagram indicates that the implementation of agile principles has not been running effectively as a whole. The identified obstacles are not only technical, but also structural and cultural, which are rooted in the traditional bureaucratic approach that has not completely changed and the lack of Disdukcapil in mastering the dynamics and conditions in its service environment, related to the conditions of geography and the demographic quality of its people, both transportation problems, assistance and the quality of its people who do not evenly understand the operational technology of services, which only urban communities recognize and understand.

In the context of the Bandung Regency Population and Civil Registry Service, the principles of fast technology-based services have begun to be implemented, but have not been fully integrated and do not guarantee of good service according to agile principles. There is still a gap between system design and reality in the field, especially in areas with difficult geographic conditions and limited infrastructure.

Limitations and Critical Reflection

This study has limitations in the number of informants and the limited observation time. In addition, KPI measurements were conducted qualitatively and did not use large-scale survey instruments. However, these results still provide a strong picture of the real conditions in the field and are an important basis for improving governance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

This study shows that the application of Agile Governance principles in the population data service system at the Bandung Regency Disdukcapil has shown positive initial steps, especially in efforts to digitize and increase service speed. However, the implementation of agile principles such as velocity, lead time, and satisfaction has not been running effectively and evenly throughout the region.

The main obstacles lie in limited human resources, inequality in community technological literacy, limited infrastructure in remote areas, and the less-than-optimal coordination system between units. This condition indicates that agile transformation in the public sector requires not only system changes, but also changes in work culture and strong structural support.

In terms of KPI indicators:

- Velocity shows an increase in basic services, but is still weak in complex services and in areas with difficult access.
- Lead Time tends to be unstable because it is influenced by geographical differences and the number of officers.
- Public satisfaction is relatively high in urban areas, but low in areas with limited technology access.

Overall, the implementation of Agile Governance in the Bandung Regency Population and Civil Registry Office is still partial and requires strategic intervention to be truly effective and inclusive.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and analysis conducted, several recommendations that can be given include:

1. Improving HR Competence

Providing routine technical and managerial training to service officers so that they are able to understand and apply agile principles consistently.

2. Expanding Digital Infrastructure

Developing a user-friendly online service system and providing mobile service units for hard- to-reach areas.

3. Mapping and Placement of Officers Based on Regional Density

Adjusting the number of service officers to the needs and demographic characteristics of the area, especially in areas with an unbalanced ratio of officers to residents.

4. Strengthening Cross-Institutional Collaboration and Local Communities

Encouraging synergy between the Population and Civil Registry Office, village governments, and community volunteers to expand the reach of digital services and education.

5. Real-Time Evaluation Based on KPI

Implementing a monitoring and evaluation system based on KPI data periodically so that the improvement process can be carried out more quickly, transparently, and measurably.

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